

It is observed that crystalline haemolysin is most stable at p_H 6.0 and is inactivated both in acid or alkaline solution. The rate of inactivation in the alkaline solution is much greater than in comparable concentration of acid solution. On neutralising alkali-inactivated solution, no regaining of the activity was observed.

Heating also inactivates haemolysin to a moderate degree and half-inactivation temperature of crystalline haemolysin was found to be 62° . But the haemolysin in crude venom was not inactivated by heating at 62° , rather the activity was slightly increased. This is probably due to the fact that some other inert protein, which is acting as an inhibitor, is absorbed on haemolysin molecules in crude venom, and the inert protein protects the haemolysin molecules from the effect of heat, it being denatured preferentially to the haemolysin.

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PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES ON HAEMOLYSIN. PART III. ISO-ELECTRIC POINT OF HAEMOLYSIN

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The iso-electric point of crystalline haemolysin has been determined both by the micro-cataphoretic method and the U-tube method and has been found to be at p_H 8.55 by the first method and 8.61 by the second method.

Of the different properties which characterise an enzyme, the determination of the iso-electric point is of considerable importance. Every protein molecule has a charge, which depends on the reaction of the medium in which it is dissolved. The p_H at which the charge of the protein is practically nil is called the iso-electric point of the protein. The iso-electric point coincides with a minimum for many of the physico-chemical properties of a protein, including cataphoresis, conductivity, solubility and osmotic pressure. The iso-electric point is affected by the buffer used for the measurement, since the charge on a colloidal particle may be affected not only by hydrogen ion but also by other ions present. It is known that if a protein solution is shaken with colloidal particles, the particles adsorb the protein and possess the same charge as that of the protein. It has been shown by Loeb (*J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1923, 6, 105) that iso-electric point of gelatine or of egg-albumin, measured either when in solution or adsorbed on the surface of microscopic particles, gives fairly concordant results. Abramson (*ibid.*, 1932, 15, 575) also compared his results for the electric mobility of serum albumin adsorbed on quartz surface and

measured by the microscopic method of electrophoresis and the data of Tiselius (*Nova acta reg. Soc. Sc., Upoaliensis*, 1930, 7, No 4) for the same protein in U-tubes and found approximate agreement between the mobilities obtained by the two methods. He, however, noticed that the iso-electric point shifted slightly due to adsorption.

Recently, Moyer (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, 122, 641) showed that the electric mobility of horse-serum, pseudoglobulin adsorbed on collodion particles, was the same as the electric mobility of the protein in the dissolved state. For determining iso-electric point the protein is generally coated on collodion or quartz particles and the charge of the particle is observed at different p_H values. The point at which the charge shifts from the positive to negative is taken to be the iso-electric point of the protein in the above medium. The buffer index is also used in determining the iso-electric point of a protein. A definite amount of protein is mixed with buffer solutions of different p_H values and p_H of the buffer, which shows the minimum shift from its original value, is taken to be the iso-electric point of the protein. In the cataphoretic method the iso-electric point is determined by studying the movement of the protein solution in a U-tube in an electric field. The iso-electric point of crystalline haemolysin (De, *Ann. Biochem. Exptl. Med.*, 1944 4, 45) has been determined by the cataphoretic method using a solution of the haemolysin itself and a suspension of quartz particles coated with the haemolysin. The iso-electric points observed in both the experiments were found to agree fairly with each other.

EXPERIMENTAL

Micro-cataphoretic Method.—A standard amount of aqueous suspension of quartz (Abramson, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1929, 13, 169) was placed in contact with stock crystalline haemolysin solution and after a few minutes the solution was diluted by the addition of a buffer solution so that the resultant buffer mixture had an ionic strength of 0.02M. The buffer solutions were those prescribed by Sorenson. Phosphate and borate buffers were used between p_H 6.0 and p_H 7.8 and p_H 8.0 and p_H 9.6 respectively. The final protein concentration was 0.2 per cent. The cataphoretic velocity of the quartz particles was observed in a flat rectangular cell of the Abramson type ("Electrokinetic Phenomena", Chemical Catalog Co., New York, 1934). The p_H of the different solutions was verified by measurement with glass electrodes and the specific conductance of each solution was measured by a Wheatstone bridge. The iso-electric point of haemolysin as determined by this method was 8.55 (Fig. 1).

Cataphoretic Method (U tube).—The apparatus consists of a U-tube with stop-cock on each side and at the same height. Also there is a side-tube of narrower bore, connected to the bottom of the U-tube. This is also provided with a stop-cock. A 0.1% crystalline haemolysin in N/15-borate buffer is poured into the side-tube, so that the U-tube is filled up to the lower ends of the stop-cocks. The stop-cock in the side-tube was then closed. The bore of each stop-cock was filled with

buffer solution of the same concentration as was used for dissolving the haemolysin by closing the other stop-cock and pouring the buffer solution carefully from the top of the tube.

FIG. 1.

Electric mobility curve of crystalline haemolysin.

The upper ends of the U-tubes were washed thoroughly with water and equal volumes of buffered solutions were placed on both ends. Connections were made with agar bridge to copper sulphate solutions to which copper-electrodes were dipped. A milliammeter was introduced in the circuit. The U-tube was fitted by a clamp and the stop-cocks opened and the current allowed to pass for a definite interval of time. The stop-cocks were then closed. The liquids in the upper ends of the tubes were transferred to two flasks and haemolytic activity was determined in both of them.

TABLE I

Electro-cataphoresis of haemolysin solution.

pH.	Units of haemolysin	
	Cathode-tube.	Anode-tube.
8.5	240	less than 10
8.56	72	" " 10
8.61	18	16
8.65	less than 10	66
8.70	" " 10	180

The iso-electric point as measured by the first method was found to be at pH 8.55 and by the second method at 8.61, which is within the limits of experimental error.

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